

TOPONYMS AS AN OBJECT OF ONOMASTICS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the study of English and Uzbek phraseological units, including place names. Attempts are being made to identify the sources of origin, as well as to analyze them from a linguocultural perspective. Toponymic phraseological units in both languages are divided into five main groups according to their sources of origin, and special attention is paid to historically connected phraseological units. Phraseological units based on specific historical events and facts are opened and explained here. The author suggests two major groups for the presence of real place names in phraseological units. The toponymic properties of real toponyms in the sense of the corresponding noun and phraseological unit have also been identified. There are also additional connotations of toponyms that affect the meaning of phraseological units. Examples are taken from a number of phraseological and paremiological dictionaries in English and Uzbek.

Key words: Toponym, onomastics, phraseological unit, Uzbek, English

Toponymy is an integral part of onomastics, which studies geographical names (toponyms), their meaning, structure, origin and distribution. The set of toponyms in any territory constitutes its toponymy (Nikonov, 2011). Traditionally, a toponym means the proper name of any geographical object, any object on the surface of the Earth or in its depths, identified by a person as an independent unit (Superanskaya, 1984), Davletkulova (2014) defines toponyms as "historically, socially and culturally defined geographical names of any natural or artificial objects created by man on land or on the water territory of the Earth. Geographical names are very stable, they persist for a long time, becoming a kind of historical monuments; therefore, toponymy, according to many researchers, also to a certain extent refers to history and source study (Nikonov, 2011; Garaeva, 2014). The status of a toponym is determined by its main functions in the linguistic culture of an ethnos: a) nominative (naming); b) individualizing (identification); c) cumulative; d) cultural content (Sedykh et al., 2020). Nikonov (2011) in his work "Introduction to Toponyms" identifies three semantic planes of toponyms: pre-toponymic, toponymic proper, and post-toponymic. (it has nothing to do with the first, since it lies in a different plane) 3)

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the toponymic (posttoponymic) meaning is the associations that connect people with a name as a result of acquaintance with an object. It is vitally important to know the post-toponymic meaning, since the meanings of pus with a toponymic element are based on it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Maslova (2005) emphasizes the role of background knowledge in the use of phraseological units with the constituent parts of a proper name, stating that the denotative aspect plays an important role in the meaning of phraseological units containing proper names. These phraseological units reflect the history of people; therefore, to understand them, you need to know specific historical facts. In all languages of the world, many phraseological units are based on the names of cities, streets, rivers, oceans, as well as on the realities associated with toponyms. PU with a toponymic component reflect a person's centuries-old observations of the world of toponymy, convey the attitude of people to this sphere of reality .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are many place names formed as part of the PU. It is important to examine how and when they appeared, as well as the determinants of their appearance. In some cases, these PUs undergo semantic transformations over time. Consequently, in the study of such phraseological units, the motivation and etymology of toponymic components play a vital role. In the process of researching the sources of origin, the following groups of software were discovered:

Shipshape and Bristol fashion - for everything to be in order (in the middle of the 19th century, Bristol was known as a port city in England. The expression emphasized the commercial prosperity of the port of Bristol and its good navigation conditions) (Shitova, 2012; Rezanova, Khlebnikova, 2015) cross the Rubicon - take irreversible action (The Rubicon was a small river in northeastern Italy. By moving his army across the Rubicon to Italy in 49 BC, Julius Caesar violated the law forbidding a general to withdraw an army from his own province, and therefore entered the war against the Senate and Pompey (Judith, 2004) In Uzbek: gap quvgan baloga yo'liqar, yo'l quvgan G'aznaga - the expression refers to the fact that Ghazna was one of the cultural, political and commercial centers of Central Asia in the Middle In most cases, the meaning of such units is closely related to the origin of PU. Thus, PU with onomastic components are an important source of information about history, culture and

tradition X. ofa Russian ethnos (Khudoyorova, 2020; Shoikova, Tikhonova, 2014).

PEs have combined customs, traditions and everyday life. Be Complete / Talk Blarney - make incomprehensible promises, flatter and deceive. The Blarney stone is a stone of the same name in Ireland. By tradition, kissing this stone, a person acquires the ability to charm and convince people (Shitova, 2012). In the Uzbek language there is PE with toponymic components related to customs and everyday life: Beva xotinga Buxorodan it huradi- so that the widow should live alone, as they gossip about her; Eshonbozorda it olsa "yigirma" sidan quruq qolmaidi - a person who goes everywhere, especially for ceremonies (Eshonbozor is a village in the south of Kazakhstan, yigirma is a religious ceremony that is held after death) ; ahmoqqa Quva bir tosh - used when a person who does not do something completely and must do it again; PUs that came from other languages: idioms and borrowings It is almost impossible to find exact synonyms for such units in other languages, thus the toponymic Pus are borrowed in most cases: in English, discover America also exists in Uzbek, Amerika ochmoq - to say or declare what has already been discovered; There are phraseological onions that exist in both languages, but in some cases they differ in meaning, for example, the Chinese wall means a barrier in English, since there has never been a unique plan for its construction, and in the Uzbek Xitoy devorimeans there is something stable and durable ... The two languages took into account different features of the same phenomenon. It should be emphasized that they are associated with world famous historical events and phenomena.

CONCLUSION

PUs containing place names in their structure have social, geographic and historical associations that are part of the background and communicative knowledge of native speakers. Facts and events of the distant past, religion, literature, customs and traditions of the nation stimulated the formation of ITS with an element of toponym. They contain culturally significant and historically related information, as a wide range of extralinguistic factors contributed to their origin. Thus, the national-cultural component of the toponym plays an important role in the semantics of such units. 2) Although most of the analyzed PU groups have similar characteristics, functions and come from the same sources in both languages, it is almost impossible to find exact parallels, except for international PU (biblical, mythological) in other languages, as they relate to unique - cultural concepts and realities every nation.

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